

Ethics Committee for Research Involving Humans
University of Silesia in Katowice
Certificate of Ethical Acceptability of Research Involving
Humans

1. Principal Investigator dr Karolina Pospiszil
2. Department: Faculty of Humanities
3. Project title: *Community-creating power of text. Upper Silesian Literature 1989-2023 / Wspólnotowórcza moc tekstu. Literatura górnośląska 1989-2023, nr UMO-2023/51/D/HS2/01035*
4. File number: KEUS/O/55/02.2026

Having reviewed the documentation of the research project indicated above, the Ethics Committee for Research Involving Humans University of Silesia in Katowice hereby confirms that the project complies with the ethical principles of conducting research involving humans. The Committee issues a positive opinion on the project, stating that:

- the documentation submitted is complete and detailed enough to assess the ethical issues arising from the research involving humans;
- the research does not violate the dignity of the participants and their right to privacy;
- the research does not pose threats to the participants or appropriate methods of the minimalization of the potential risk were ensured
- proper supervision over the implementation of the ethical standards is ensured;
- information about the research presented to the participants is reliable and understandable; free and informed consent is ensured;
- competence to conduct the research has been documented;
- the project respects intellectual property rights and personal data protection.

The opinion relates to research conducted since it was obtained.

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Chair